

Studies on some homo- and bimetallic dinuclear transition metal complexes of [2,3,6,9,12,13-hexaaza-4,5,9,11-tetraphenyl-1,14-di-(2'-hydroxyphenyl)-tetradeca-1,3,5,9,11,13-hexaene] (HTHT)

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A series of homo- and bimetallic dinuclear complexes of the type $[\text{NiM}(\text{HTHT})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_n]\text{X}_{n'}$, where $\text{M} = \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}$, Co^{II} and Ni^{II} ; $n = 0, 2$; $\text{X} = \text{Cl}^-$, NO_3^- ; $n' = 2$ have been prepared and characterised on the basis of different physico-chemical investigations. The "inner" core is occupied by Ni^{II} having N_4 -chromophore with square-planar stereochemistry while the "outer" core is occupied by the second metal ion (homo/bimetallic) having N_2O_2 chromophore and square-planar/octahedral geometry depending on the nature of the metal ion. The magnetic moment values corroborates their stereochemistry.

We have been successful in isolating some trinuclear metal complexes from the reaction of benzildihydrazone complexes and salicylaldehyde^{1,2}. Some of these complexes (hetero-nuclear) can be termed as trinuclear bimetallic complexes because two kinds of metal ions can be placed in two different ordered arrangement. In the present investigation, we report the synthesis and characterisation of some homo- and bimetallic complexes with the titled ligand which is obtained by the *in situ* reaction of ethylene (bis-benzil-monohydrazone) complexes with salicylaldehyde in the presence of metal ions.

Results and discussion

The *in situ* condensation of benzilmonohydrazone in presence of nickel(II) ion has been effective with 1,2-diaminoethane giving rise to a series of precursor complexes, ethylene bis(benzil monohydrazone)-nickel(II) (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1

In the quadratically bonded ligand, the free $-\text{NH}_2$ groups subsequently react with carbonyl groups of salicylaldehyde in the presence of homo- and bimetallic metal ions yielding dinuclear complexes. The yield of the complexes are almost quantitative. All the complexes slowly decompose above 250° . Elucidation of the structure and mode of bonding in

the complexes have been made by following spectral and magnetic data.

IR spectra :

The infrared spectra of all the complexes except Ni-Ni system exhibit an identical pattern suggesting them to be isostructural. Since the Schiff base product of the precursor could not be isolated the spectra of the present series of complexes are studied along with the precursor complex³, and the related Schiff bases.

Reaction of the precursor complex with salicylaldehyde in the presence of metal ions bring about drastic changes in the spectra of the products. The most significant feature of the spectra is the disappearance of the bands due to $-\text{NH}_2$ stretching and deformation vibrations. Absence of any band in the vicinity of 1650 cm^{-1} due to $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ of salicylaldehyde indicates that the Schiff base reaction has taken place. A slight bathchromic shift in the position of the $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ band has taken place in the binuclear complexes and is observed at around 1625 cm^{-1} as a single band. The appearance of a single band suggests that all the azomethine groups are of same vibrational energy and they participate in complexation.

The C-H stretching vibration of phenyl groups are recognised by the presence of a band around 2930 cm^{-1} in the precursor as well as in the dinuclear complexes. Besides a multiple band system in the region $1600-1450 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is observed in all complexes suggesting the presence of C=C skeletal, diagnostic of aromatic structure.

That the phenolic function undergo deprotonation and participate in the complexation is evidenced by the appearance of a band due to ν_{C-O} at $\sim 1505\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Further a medium band at around 550 cm^{-1} due to ν_{M-O} are observed⁴, which also supports our above contention.

Metal nitrogen vibrational bands which are clearly distinguishable in the precursors and in the dinuclear complexes are observed in the region 460 and 480 cm^{-1} , respectively⁵.

In addition to above bands all the complexes except Ni-Ni system show a strong band at about 3450 cm^{-1} and a band of medium intensity at 810 cm^{-1} assignable to ν_{OH} and $\rho_{H_2O(r)}$ of coordinated water molecule respectively². This is further supported from the thermal analysis which is subsequently discussed. The IR spectra of the nitrate complexes of Ni-Co system give an insight to the nature of the anionic groups. A coordinated nitrate group generally absorbs in the region around 1200 cm^{-1} . These bands are not however observed in IR spectra of the nitrate complexes suggesting the non-coordination of the anionic groups⁶. The high molar conductance values of the complexes also corroborates this observation.

Thus from the above evidence we are of the opinion that the "inner" metal centre (i.e. Ni^{II} from the precursor complex) has N_4 -chromophore, while the other metal centre (either homo- or bimetallic) has N_2O_2 chromophore. The ligand, therefore, acts as an octadentate ligand with six azomethine nitrogen atoms and two phenolic oxygen atoms coordinating to two metal centres.

Thermal analysis :

IR spectra of the bimetallic dinuclear complexes indicated presence of coordinated water. The thermograms of the complexes exhibit an identical pattern of thermal decomposition. They undergo two steps of thermal degradation. There was no weight loss upto 140° , suggesting the absence of lattice water⁷. After 140° , the first step of weight loss was encountered. The weight loss corresponds to two molecules of water. Their simultaneous elimination comparatively at a higher temperature is probably due to the coordinating nature and their existence in an identical chemical environment⁸.

A stable product continue upto 220° , after which there is an abrupt mass loss which is probably due to the oxidation of organic constituents in the complexes. The decomposition continued upto $\sim 460^\circ$ finally leaving behind the metal oxides.

Electronic spectra and magnetic properties of [Ni Ni(HTHT)]X₂ complexes :

The electronic spectral band of these complexes occur only at 22730 cm^{-1} followed by a CT band at 29000 cm^{-1} . This type of spectral features can be satisfactorily interpreted in terms of a square-planar environment around nickel(II) centres. This is also confirmed from diamagnetic nature of the complexes.

The width of the band manifests that it represent a group of two to three transitions arising out of $^1A_{2g} \rightarrow ^1A_{1g}$, $^1A_{2g} \rightarrow ^1B_{2g}$ and $^1A_{2g} \rightarrow ^1E_g$ transitions under a square-planar environment and superimposed into single one⁹. It is to be noted that though the inner nickel(II) centre has a N_4 -chromophore and the outer nickel(II) centre has an N_2O_2 -chromophore, instead of getting two distinct bands only one band at higher frequency region having higher intensity

Table 1. Analytical and molar conductance data of the complexes*

Compds.	Colour	Ni% Found (Calcd.)	Metal% ** Found (Calcd.)	Cond. $\Omega^{-1}\text{ cm}^2$ mol^{-1}
[Ni(HTHT)]Cl ₂	Orange	13.81 (13.55)	-	152
[Ni ₂ (C ₄₄ H ₃₄ N ₆ O ₂)]Cl ₂				
[Ni ₂ (HTHT)](NO ₃) ₂	Red	12.83 (12.27)	-	163
[Ni ₂ (C ₄₄ H ₃₄ N ₆ O ₂)]NO ₃) ₂				
[NiCu(HTHT)(H ₂ O) ₂](NO ₃) ₂	Brown	6.38 (6.47)	6.89 (7.00)	156
[NiCu(C ₄₄ H ₃₈ N ₆ O ₄)]Cl ₂				
[NiCu(HTHT)(H ₂ O) ₂](NO ₃) ₂	Blue	5.98 (6.61)	6.59 (6.61)	159
[NiCu(C ₄₄ H ₃₈ N ₆ O ₄)](NO ₃) ₂				
[NiCo(HTHT)(H ₂ O) ₂](NO ₃) ₂	Brown	6.39 (6.50)	6.47 (6.52)	166
[NiCo(C ₄₄ H ₃₈ N ₆ O ₄)]Cl ₂				
[NiCo(HTHT)(H ₂ O) ₂](NO ₃) ₂	Brown	6.05 (6.14)	6.02 (6.11)	169
[NiCo(C ₄₄ H ₃₈ N ₆ O ₄)](NO ₃) ₂				

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

**M = Co, Cu.

Table 2. Structural parameters of [NiM(HTHT)(H₂O)_n]X₂ complexes as determined from X-ray powder diffraction

M = Cu^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}; n = 0, 2

Complex	a	b	c	c/a	in degree			Vol.	Crystal system
					α	β	γ		
[Ni ₂ (HTHT)](NO ₃) ₂	15.57	12.26	8.86	0.57	90.00	90.00	90.00	1690.5	Orthorhombic
[NiCu(HTHT)(H ₂ O) ₂](NO ₃) ₂	12.48	14.28	7.52	0.60	104.13	90.86	93.26	1296.5	Monoclinic
[NiCo(HTHT)(H ₂ O) ₂](NO ₃) ₂	11.52	13.69	11.69	1.00	116.23	82.42	111.94	1515.08	Triclinic

than that of the precursor complex was observed. However the CT band remain unaltered. This suggests that the crystal field strength due to "N₃-chromophore" and "N₂O₂-chromophore" of the ligand framework probably are of same strength.

[Ni Cu(HTHT)(H₂O)₂]X₂ complexes :

The electronic spectra of the complexes display mainly two broad bands at ~23810 and ~14285 cm⁻¹ followed by a CT band at 29000 cm⁻¹. The spectral features reveal that the former band might be due to inner nickel(II) centre in square-planar environment which is shifted to higher frequency region compared to precursor complex, whereas the later band is a broad envelop due to the outer copper(II) centre in an approximately distorted octahedral environment and is due to ²E_g → ²T_{2g} transition. The width and asymmetry of the band provide evidence for a strong Jahn-Teller distortion.

The inner nickel(II) centre being diamagnetic, the observed magnetic moment values of the complexes lie in the range 1.78 to 1.84 B.M. commensurating with spin free hexa coordinated copper(II) centre.

[Ni Co(HTHT)(H₂O)₂]X₂ complexes :

A close examination of the electronic spectra of these complexes reveals that a broad band in the region 10000 cm⁻¹ is observed. This can be assigned to ⁴T_{1g} → ⁴T_{2g} (F) (ν₁) transition due to outer cobalt(II) ion in an octahedral symmetry¹⁰. A doubly split band in the region 18690 and 17540 cm⁻¹ was observed. This may be due to split component of ν₃ band due to ⁴T_{1g} (F) → ⁴T_{1g} (P) transition of the outer cobalt(II) centre. The multiplicity of such band can be interpreted due to six coordinated cobalt(II) centre of an approximately C_{2v} symmetry¹⁰. Besides the above bands the precursor band at 22200 cm⁻¹ due to ²A_{2g} → ¹A_{1g} transition which is shifted to higher frequency is also observed.

The RT magnetic moment values of these complexes lie in the range 4.38 to 4.42 B.M. This values are lower than those expected for high spin octahedral cobalt(II) complexes. This value may arise due to distorted six coordinated cobalt(II) centre of approximately C₂-symmetry.

X-Ray diffraction studies :

X-ray diffraction patterns of the powder samples of the complexes suggest them to be crystalline in nature. Good number of reflections are observed in the diffractograms. The structures of these powders were determined using the LSUCRIPC programme developed by Garvery of North Dakota University. The structure of Ni-Ni complex was found to be orthorhombic, whereas other two complexes were monoclinic and triclinic. These results indicate that when

Cu and Co are replaced in the system, the structure goes to lower symmetry. This observation is further substantiated from the electronic spectral measurements in these compounds. The detailed structural data is presented in Table 2. It is observed that the axial ratio (*c/a*) increases with change in nickel ion to copper or cobalt ion.

Structure of the complexes :

On the basis of the foregoing observations the following tentative structure for the dinuclear complexes have been proposed.

when M = Cu²⁺, Co²⁺; X = H₂O
and when M = Ni²⁺; X = O

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Solvents were distilled prior to their use. Other chemicals were used as such. Benzilmonohydrazone and the precursor Ni^{II} complexes were prepared following literature methods³. The homo- and bimetallic metal complexes were prepared following two different methods as exemplified below. However, in both the cases metal complexes of same stoichiometry were isolated.

Method I : The precursor complex [Ni(EBMH)]Cl₂ (0.601 g, 1 mmol) was suspended in hot dry ethanol and refluxed for 0.5 h. To it salicylaldehyde (0.244 g, 2 mmol) was added dropwise and was refluxed for 0.5 h followed by drop wise addition of nickel(II) chloride hexahydrate (0.237 g, 1 mmol) in absolute ethanol. The mixture was refluxed further for 3 h, when a deep brown solution was obtained. The volume was reduced to half and then cooled to RT and the resultant deep brown solid was washed several times with dry ethanol and dried over fused calcium chloride.

The other homo- and bimetallic dinuclear complexes of HTHT were prepared similarly by adding appropriate metal salts in definite proportions.

Method II : The precursor complexes were prepared *in situ* by taking appropriate proportions of benzilmonohydrazone (0.448 g, 2 mmol), nickel(II) chloride hexahydrate (0.237 g, 1 mmol) and ethylene diamine (0.06 g, 1 mmol) in the ratio 2 : 1 : 1 and refluxing the resulting

solution for 8 h. To it salicylaldehyde (0.244 g, 2 mmol) was added and refluxed for another 0.5 h. Then nickel(II) chloride hexahydrate (0.237 g, 1 mmol) in ethanol was added dropwise to it and was further refluxed for 3 h. The volume of the solution was reduced to half. It was cooled to RT and the resulting deep brown solid was washed with cold absolute ethanol and dried over fused calcium chloride.

The other homo- and bimetallic dinuclear complexes were prepared similarly by adding appropriate metal salts to the precursor solutions in definite proportions.

The metal and nitrogen were estimated by known methods. C and H were estimated with a MLW-CHN microanalyser. Molecular weight was determined by Rast's method. The reflectance and IR spectra in KBr were recorded on Cary 2390 and Perkin-Elmer 983 spectrophotometers, respectively. The conductivities of the complexes in dioxan were measured with a Toshniwal conductivity bridge. The RT magnetic moments were determined by Gouy method with $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_4]$ as the calibrant. Thermogravimetric analyses in air were carried out by a Netzsch-429 simultaneous recording TGA and DTA thermoanalyser instrument at a heating rate of $10^\circ \text{ min}^{-1}$. Around 50–100 mg of the sample was used in each case.

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